

Rac-1ac

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-147-s-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	10132
Vial:	77	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 147 S RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	7.9 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/13/2021 9:13:28 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/13/2021 9:37:53 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.841	11852359	49.95	1366135
2	7.092	11875214	50.05	

Asy-1ac

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-147-3-s-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	10133
Vial:	75	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 147 3 S
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	7.9 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/13/2021 9:25:46 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/13/2021 9:35:39 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.939	13483	0.26	860
2	6.898	5154257	99.74	455912